

Sustainable biostimulant strategy through microalgae-based recycling of horticultural fertigation drainage management

Tatiana P.L. Cunha–Chiamolera^{a,*}, Miguel Urrestarazu^a, Francisco Gabriel Acién-Fernández^b, Cintia Gómez-Serrano^b, Adrián Guirao-García^a, Silvia Jimenez-Becker^{a,c}, Raúl Ortega^{a,c}, Isabel Miralles^{a,c}

^a Department of Agronomy, University of Almería, Almería 04120, Spain

^b Department Chemical Engineering–CIESOL, University of Almería, Almería 04120, Spain

^c Centre for Intensive Mediterranean Agrosystems and Agri–Food Biotechnology, University of Almería, Almería E-04120, Spain

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ABSTRACT

The reuse of horticultural drainage water represents a promising strategy to scarcity and promote sustainability in intensive agriculture. This study evaluates the potential of a microalgae-based treatment system for fertigation management through the purification of drainage water from a hydroponic tomato crop grown in coconut fibre substrate. Using *Scenedesmus* sp. in raceway reactors, we analyzed the efficiency of ion removal, microbial community dynamics, and microalgal biomass productivity. Results demonstrated that microalgae treatment effectively reduced concentrations of key nutrients and trace elements—such as nitrate, phosphate, calcium, and iron—while maintaining stable electrical conductivity. Biomass productivity ($15.42 \pm 2.34 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) was comparable to that achieved with synthetic media, confirming the viability of agricultural effluents as a growth substrate. The microbial analysis revealed that, although some beneficial microorganisms declined, the system significantly reduced pathogenic taxa and enriched microbial genes involved in carbon degradation and phosphorus cycling. These changes suggest that treated water can enhance nutrient availability, especially in soils with organic amendments or alkaline pH. Moreover, fertigation trials using the treated water on lettuce showed improved nutrient uptake and crop yield, along with mitigation of osmotic stress effects. Overall, the results highlight the agronomic, environmental, and economic benefits of integrating microalgae-based treatment systems in horticulture. This approach represents a practical model of circular economy, enhancing irrigation efficiency, reducing pollution, and promoting sustainable bioresource utilization.

1. Introduction

In recent decades, the implementation of water reuse strategies—particularly through closed fertigation systems and the recycling of drainage water from soilless culture—has gained increasing attention due to their substantial economic, environmental, and social implications. These approaches have been extensively studied since the 1980s, with early investigations by Adams (1980) and Zekki et al. (1996) providing foundational insights into drain water recovery and nutrient reuse. More recent studies, such as those by García-Caparrós et al. (2018) and Asaduzzaman et al. (2022), have further advanced this knowledge by evaluating system performance, sustainability metrics, and technological innovations for optimized nutrient management. So,

achieving viable water and nutrient reuse from drainage in soilless agriculture requires an integrated strategy that involves managing fertigation volumes, correcting nutrient imbalances, and fine-tuning the final nutrient solution to optimize crop performance. In contrast, conventional open fertigation systems in greenhouse crop production typically result in significant drainage losses, with drain fractions ranging from 20 % to 40 % of applied water (Schröder and Lieth, 2002; Urrestarazu and Carrasco, 2023). These losses contribute to environmental pollution through the leaching of nitrates and phosphates, which are primary drivers of soil contamination and eutrophication in surrounding water bodies and aquifers. Consequently, transitioning toward closed-loop systems represents a critical step in achieving sustainable and environmentally responsible horticultural practices.

* Correspondence to: University of Almería, Department of Agronomy, Carretera Sacramento s/n, La Cañada de San Urbano, Almería 04120, Spain.

E-mail addresses: tatipcc@ual.es (T.P.L. Cunha–Chiamolera), mgavilan@ual.es (M. Urrestarazu), facien@ual.es (F.G. Acién-Fernández), cinti4201@hotmail.com (C. Gómez-Serrano), aaguirao4b@gmail.com (A. Guirao-García), sbecker@ual.es (S. Jimenez-Becker), rortega@ual.es (R. Ortega), imiralles@ual.es (I. Miralles).

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A major limitation of water reuse strategies in closed soilless systems is the gradual increase in the electrical conductivity (EC) of the irrigation solution, which can negatively affect crop performance if not properly managed. This rise in EC is primarily due to two processes: (1) the preferential absorption of water over nutrient ions by plants, leading to the concentration of solutes in the remaining solution, and (2) the relatively low uptake rates of certain ions, particularly sodium (Na^+) and chloride (Cl^-), which tend to accumulate in the root-zone solution over successive irrigation cycles. As a result, the EC of the drainage water in closed systems often exceeds that of the initial nutrient solution. To address this challenge, predictive models have been developed to simulate the EC dynamics and guide management practices to prevent excessive salt buildup and ensure nutrient balance (Urrestarazu and García, 2000; Savvas, 2002). In this context, tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*), a crop of major economic importance worldwide, is widely cultivated under both open and closed fertigation systems, making it a relevant model for evaluating nutrient dynamics and water reuse efficiency. Similarly, lettuce (*Lactuca sativa*) is extensively used in horticultural research due to its rapid growth cycle, sensitivity to salinity, and suitability for hydroponic systems, providing a robust model for controlled studies on nutrient uptake and saline water management (Peçanha et al., 2021; Cunha-Chiamolera et al., 2024; Góis et al., 2024). Therefore, under the principles of circular horticulture, it is essential to rigorously assess and compare different techniques for drain water reuse versus open systems to enhance sustainability, optimize resource use, and minimize environmental impact.

The treatment and reuse of agricultural drainage water represent a crucial strategy for implementing circular economy principles in intensive farming systems. Among various available methods, microalgae-based treatment systems have emerged as highly promising due to their dual capacity for wastewater purification and biomass generation. These systems operate through microalgae-bacteria consortia that effectively remove organic matter, nutrients (nitrogen and phosphorus), and pathogens including bacteria, protozoa, and fungi. Microalgae treatment has demonstrated high removal efficiencies for microbial contaminants, often exceeding 90 %, and also significantly reduces the presence of contaminants of emerging concern such as pharmaceuticals and endocrine disruptors. Compared to traditional biological treatments like activated sludge or biofilters, microalgae offer distinct advantages: lower energy consumption ($<0.2 \text{ kWh m}^{-3}$), reduced treatment costs ($<0.2 \text{ € m}^{-3}$), and generation of valuable biomass ($>1 \text{ € kg}^{-1}$) that can be repurposed as biofertilizers or animal feed (Femeena et al., 2022). Beyond wastewater detoxification, the treated water has been shown to enhance crop yields and root nutrient absorption, while the microbial ecosystem shifts towards a more beneficial composition. This holistic approach exemplifies how integrating microalgae into agricultural systems supports wastewater reuse, pathogen mitigation, and resource recovery, thus fulfilling key objectives of circular and sustainable agriculture (Cunha-Chiamolera et al., 2024).

Microalgae have garnered substantial attention as natural biostimulants in agriculture due to their rich content of biologically active compounds that can significantly enhance plant growth and resilience. These unicellular organisms produce a wide array of metabolites—including plant growth hormones, polysaccharides, amino acids, vitamins, and antioxidants—that improve nutrient uptake, stimulate root development, increase photosynthetic efficiency, and bolster plants' ability to withstand abiotic stresses such as drought, salinity, and heavy metals (Morillas-España et al., 2024). Moreover, microalgae-derived biostimulants have demonstrated the capacity to enhance crop yields, fruit quality, and resistance to pathogens through foliar application, soil drenching, or seed treatment. Studies show that these biostimulants also help modulate plant hormone signaling pathways and induce systemic resistance, contributing to better plant health under stress conditions (Kumar et al., 2022). Importantly, their use aligns with sustainable agricultural practices, offering an eco-friendly alternative to synthetic agrochemicals and reducing the environmental footprint of crop

production. Recent reviews emphasize that while the commercial adoption of microalgal biostimulants is still growing, they hold transformative potential for the future of eco-efficient farming (Chabili et al., 2024).

Despite the growing interest in sustainable water reuse, limited research exists on the reuse of treated water from microalgae-based processes in agriculture. However, recent findings highlight its substantial potential. In a pilot-scale study using *Scenedesmus almeriensis*, microalgae achieved remarkable removal efficiencies for pharmaceutical contaminants—up to 99 % for metronidazole and 98 % for diclofenac—with negligible residues in the resulting biomass, thus affirming the safety of the treated water for irrigation purposes (Morillas-España et al., 2025). This process not only purifies the water but also recovers essential macronutrients like nitrogen and phosphorus, which are crucial for plant growth and reduce dependency on synthetic fertilizers. The application of this regenerated water in horticulture has demonstrated positive impacts on crop productivity, soil microbial diversity, and water-use efficiency, thereby enhancing resource circularity and lowering environmental burdens (Cunha-Chiamolera et al., 2024). Another critical benefit of microalgae treatment is its ability to remove pathogenic microorganisms, which pose serious public health risks. Microalgae combat pathogens through multiple mechanisms: competing for nutrients, elevating pH and oxygen levels, facilitating microbial sedimentation, and producing algicidal compounds (El-Aswar et al., 2022; Abdelfattah et al., 2023). These biochemical and ecological interactions create hostile conditions for pathogen survival, positioning microalgae-based systems as a multifunctional and sustainable solution for agricultural water reuse in circular economy frameworks.

On the other hand, microorganisms present in irrigation and fertigation water, even in small proportions (Tyskiewicz et al., 2022; Ortega et al., 2023), have been recognized as playing an important role—despite ongoing debate regarding the relative impact of general ionic effects (i.e., salinity measured via electrical conductivity) versus specific ionic effects (Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009).

This study investigates the reuse of microalgae-treated drainage water from tomato crops in soilless systems, focusing on its safety and potential agronomic benefits. It aims to assess whether the treated effluent poses any toxicological risks and to explore its positive effects linked to its chemical and microbial composition. The research also evaluates the biostimulant potential of both untreated and treated water, considering how such effluents might enhance plant growth or stress resilience, offering farmers sustainable irrigation alternatives within circular agricultural practices.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Microalgae-related drainage treatment

The drainage water used in this study was sourced from a soilless culture tomato crop (cv. “Margymeno”) cultivated on coconut fiber substrate within a ‘raspa y amagado’ style greenhouse at the IFAPA La Cañada research center in Almería, Spain, under the AGROCONNECT project. This nutrient-rich drainage was treated in an 80 m^2 raceway photobioreactor located at the SABANA Demo Plant, also at IFAPA, which operated with a 12 m^3 culture volume and a 0.15 m depth. Environmental parameters such as pH and dissolved oxygen were precisely regulated using CO_2 and air injection systems. A parallel control reactor was maintained under identical conditions but used a synthetic fertilizer-based medium optimized for microalgae growth (containing NaNO_3 , KH_2PO_4 , and MgSO_4), as described by Nordio et al. (2023). Both systems were inoculated with *Scenedesmus* sp., a microalga known for its robustness in variable pH and temperature and its efficiency in nutrient uptake and oxygenation, making it ideal for wastewater treatment (Morillas-España et al., 2024; Nordio et al., 2024).

Following a one-week batch inoculation phase, the systems transitioned to continuous operation with a dilution rate of 0.2 day^{-1} , meaning

2400 L of drainage was exchanged daily. Once steady-state conditions were achieved, the cultures were sustained for an additional three weeks. Biomass production was quantified daily through filtration and drying techniques, and mineral content analysis was performed pre- and post-treatment by the University of Almería's Central Services Laboratory. At the end of the culture cycle, the microalgal suspension was centrifuged, recovering 99 % of the biomass, while the resulting supernatant (treated water) was used in fertigation trials on lettuce crops, thus closing the loop between wastewater remediation and agricultural reuse. This process not only evaluated the purification efficacy of microalgae but also assessed the agronomic viability of using the treated effluent as a nutrient-rich irrigation resource.

2.2. Microbiological characterization

2.2.1. DNA extraction and quality control

Microbial DNA present in 500 mL of untreated (UW) and microalgae treated water (MTW) were extracted using an E.Z.N.A® Water DNA kit (Omega Bio-Tek) following the manufacturer's instructions and the concentration was measured by Qubit (Thermo Fisher) before library preparation. The possible genomic DNA degradation was measured using the fragment analyzer platform AATI (Agilent Technologies).

2.2.2. Library preparation, Quality Control and Sequencing

Libraries were prepared using the kit Novogene NGS DNA Library Prep Set (Cat No.PT004). Briefly; 200 ng of genomic DNA was randomly sheared into short fragments using a Covaris ultrasonic disruptor. The obtained fragments were end-repaired, A-tailed, and further ligated with Illumina adapters. The fragments with adapters were size-selected 350 bp, PCR amplified, and purified. The libraries were checked with Qubit and real-time PCR for quantification and a Bioanalyzer for size distribution detection. Quantified libraries were pooled and sequenced on the Illumina platform Novaseq X plus, and paired-end reads were generated (strategy PE150) according to the effective library concentration and the 2 Gb data amount required.

2.2.3. Bioinformatics Analysis Pipeline

Metagenomic samples were quality-controlled and trimmed for adapters using fastp tool. Considering the possibility of host contamination in samples, clean data needs to be blasted to the host database to filter out reads that may come from the host origin. Bowtie2 software (Langmead and Salzberg, 2012) is used by default, with the following parameter settings: end-to-end, sensitive, -I 200, and -X 400 (Karlsson et al., 2012, 2013; Scher et al., 2013). Using Kraken 2.1.3 (<https://github.com/DerrickWood/kraken2>), microbial sequences were compared against a database built with kraken2-build (parameters -threads 5 -quick -gzip-compressed) and the species annotation results were corrected using Braken 2.9 (<https://ccb.jhu.edu/software/bracken/>) (Lu et al., 2017). Diamond 2.1.8 (<http://www.diamondsearch.org>) was used to align sequences against the UniProt database (parameter settings blastx -p 6 -e 1e-5 -id 80 -top 1) (Bateman et al., 2025), and the annotation results for KEGG databases (Version 2023), were obtained based on the correspondence with UniRef90 IDs. According to Du et al. (2023), genes related to C, N, and P cycles and processes were identified and their RPK relative abundances resulted from the sum of the abundance of the genes annotated to the same feature.

2.3. Lettuce growth experiments

The lettuce growth experiments were conducted in a culture chamber of the Climate Control and Soilless Culture Laboratory of the University of Almería, Spain, from September to October 2024. Seedlings with four true leaves of lettuce cv. "Maravilla de verano" was transplanted into 250 mL pots filled with coconut fibre, whose physical characteristics have been described by Rodríguez et al. (2014). Plants were grown with a light-dark cycle of 16–8 h, day-night temperature of

25–20° C, relative humidity of 55–75 % and photosynthetic photon flux density of 250 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ (400–700 nm) supplied by L18 T8 AP67 LED lamps (Valoya, Helsinki, Finland) during a 23-day cycle. A total of six different types of fertigation treatment has been used. The proportion of macro- and micro nutrients in the nutrition solution was as recommended by Sonneveld and Straver (1994), using the water irrigation showed in Table 1. Good- (T0g) and medium-quality (T0m) irrigation water were used as controls, considering two possible options for farmers (Table 2). Four treatments involving the reuse of drains were carried out: two of these used microalgae-treated drains, depending on whether the irrigation water was of good (TAg) or medium quality (TAm). The second two used untreated drains, labelled TSg and TSm, for good and medium quality irrigation water, respectively.). The procedure to obtain the fertigation for each of the treatments is shown in Fig. 1.

Fertigation management in the experiment was carried out following the criteria of Peçanha et al., 2021 and Urrestarazu and Carrasco (2023). The application of new fertigation was supplied when the water in the crop unit reached 10 % of the readily available water, and the necessary volume was added to obtain between 15 % and 25 % drainage (Peçanha et al., 2021). The pH, electrical conductivity (EC), nitrate and potassium content of the nutritive solution and the drainage volume (fraction between input volume and output volume from the crop unit in relation to fertigation supplied) were measured using a Crison MM40 + pH meter (Hach® LPV2500.98.0002, Loveland, CO, USA), an EC-Meter Crison BASIC 30 conductivity meter (Hach® LPV2500.98.0002, Loveland, Colorado, USA), and a LAQUATwin B-742 and B-731 (Horiba®, Moulton, Northampton, UK), respectively. Ratio of drainage was measured using a test tube graduated to one hundredth of a millimeter.

Lettuce growth was measured through fresh mass and dry mass harvested 23 days after transplanting. Plants were separated into root, stem and leaves, weighed and then placed for drying in a forced air circulation oven (Thermo Scientific Heratherm, Germany) at 95° C until constant weight was maintained. Weights were measured using an OHAUS Adventurer precision analytical balance model AX 124/E (OHAUS Europe GmbH, Nänikon, Switzerland), with an accuracy of four-tenths of a gram.

2.4. Statistical analysis and experimental design

The experiment was conducted under a randomized complete block design with six treatments, 4 replicates, and 6 plants per replicate, for biological and technical analysis (Petersen, 1994). The results were subjected to an analysis of variance (ANOVA) and subsequent separation of means by Tukey's test ($p \leq 0.05$), using Statgraphics Centurion® XVI.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Performance of microalgae-related wastewater treatment process on hydroponic crop tomato drainage

The performance of microalgae in treating drainage water was assessed concurrently with biomass productivity during the steady-state phase of the culture. As detailed in Table 1, the nutrient composition of untreated water (UW) and microalgae-treated water (MTW) from a tomato hydroponic system was compared. Despite the treatment, the electrical conductivity (EC) remained constant at 3.2 dS m^{-1} , indicating a stable total ionic load. However, marked reductions were noted in nitrate (NO_3^-), phosphate (H_2PO_4^-), calcium (Ca^{2+}), magnesium (Mg^{2+}), and several micronutrients such as iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), and boron (B)—elements efficiently absorbed by *Scenedesmus* sp. during microalgal growth (Morillas-España et al., 2025). In contrast, sulfate (SO_4^{2-}) and potassium (K^+) levels showed minimal change, and chloride (Cl^-) and sodium (Na^+) levels increased, likely due to evaporation-induced concentration rather than biological uptake (Nordio et al., 2024). In any case, it is well known that the interaction between salinity (i.e., the general osmotic effect) and specific macro-

Table 1

Average electrical conductivity (EC) and main mineral contents in irrigation waters (IW) and drains of untreated and microalgae-treated waters used in fertigation during the crop cycle.

IW	EC dS m ⁻¹	mM								μM				
		NO ₃ ⁻	H ₂ PO ₄ ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	Cl ⁻	K ⁺	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	Na ⁺	Fe	Mn	Cu	Zn	B
Good	0.12	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.99	0.01	0.08	0.05	0.94	0.18	0.02	0.16	0.59	37.46
Medium	1.14	0.11	0.03	0.45	10.61	0.08	1.45	1.33	6.87	0.18	0.02	0.16	0.38	43.38
IW From crop drain														
Untreated (UW)	3.20	12.42	3.85	8.89	8.38	12.19	5.88	5.07	7.50	106	42.9	6.23	11.24	107.48
Microalgae treated (MTW)	3.20	9.46	0.73	8.73	9.69	12.31	1.61	3.97	13.81	5.59	1.11	3.02	3.19	80.65

Table 2

Main parameters and composition of the different fertigation systems supplied for the tomato crop drain reuse trial treated with a microalgae culture compared to standard controls.

Acronym	Description	Irrigation water		Reused water		Concentrated fertiliser tanks (CF)		Final fertigation	
		EC	Ratio	EC	Ratio	EC	Ratio	EC	[NO ₃] mM
Tog	Optimum irrigation water (g, EC ≤ 0.25) + CF	0.25	0.9900	-	-	175.00	0.0100	2.00	10.00
TSg	g + untreated drain water (S) + CF	0.25	0.9700	3.20	0.0200	175.00	0.0100	2.06	10.00
TAg	g + microalgae-treated drain water (A) + CF	0.25	0.9700	3.20	0.0200	175.00	0.0100	2.06	10.00
T0m	Suboptimum irrigation water (m, EC ≥ 0.95) + CF	0.95	0.9910	-	-	175.00	0.0085	2.43	8.50
TSm	m + S + CF	0.95	0.9710	3.20	0.0200	175.00	0.0085	2.47	8.50
TAm	m + A + CF	0.95	0.9710	3.20	0.0200	175.00	0.0085	2.47	8.50

EC= Electrical conductivity (dS m⁻¹).

Fig. 1. Schematic of the potential water and nutrient reuse of a soilless crop with some of the possible mix and combination methods of the fluids involved and methodology of experiment. The letters in brackets show that they are receiving treatment.

and micronutrient concentrations (i.e., specific ionic effects) leads to complex physiological responses in crops that are often difficult to distinguish and interpret (Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009).

When compared with conventional culture media used in large-scale microalgae cultivation—such as synthetic formulations enriched with 0.9 g L⁻¹ NaNO₃, 0.14 g L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄, and 0.18 g L⁻¹ MgSO₄—the MTW presented a nutrient profile with comparable macronutrient content and a more diverse array of trace elements (Nordio et al., 2023). This

naturally occurring complexity could provide a cost-effective and sustainable alternative to synthetic media, especially in open or semi-closed raceway reactors used in circular bioeconomy applications. Additionally, despite the stable EC, the shift in ion-specific composition highlights the importance of evaluating individual nutrients for optimizing microalgae productivity and ensuring the agronomic safety of fertigation reuse (Cunha-Chiamolera et al., 2024). These findings support the viability of treated drainage water not only as a treatment output but

also as a valuable input for microalgae cultivation and irrigation, aligning with sustainable agriculture goals.

The biological performance of the microalgae cultivation system fed with treated agricultural drainage was evaluated during its steady-state operation. The resulting biomass concentration averaged $0.51 \pm 0.08 \text{ g L}^{-1}$, with a biomass productivity of $15.42 \pm 2.34 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, while the control culture using a standard synthetic fertilizer medium achieved a similar biomass concentration of $0.52 \pm 0.02 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ and productivity of $15.48 \pm 0.72 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$. The absence of significant differences between the two conditions highlights that microalgae can grow equally well using drainage water, confirming its effectiveness as a sustainable alternative to conventional nutrient sources. These productivity values are consistent with those obtained in comparable systems. For instance, Do et al. (2020) reported that *Chlorella variabilis* consortia cultivated in raceway reactors treating domestic wastewater reached productivities between 11.1 and $15.3 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, closely mirroring the figures observed in the current study (Do et al., 2020).

Similarly, a long-term evaluation using *Scenedesmus almeriensis* in raceways supplied with urban wastewater reported average productivities of $13 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ over several months (Cai, 2013), while seasonal studies showed peaks of $25.1 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ in summer and lows of $12.3 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ in winter, depending on sunlight and temperature conditions (Morillas-España et al., 2021). The current values—recorded in April—thus fall within this typical seasonal range, further validating the efficiency and robustness of agricultural drainage as a culture medium. Overall, these comparisons underscore the feasibility of integrating microalgae cultivation with agricultural water reuse systems, offering not only competitive biomass yields but also aligning with circular economy goals in sustainable agriculture.

3.2. Effect of wastewater management on the microbiotic populations

3.2.1. Taxonomic annotations

The microorganisms present in the water samples were constituted in their big majority by bacteria (>99 %) with very low abundances of archaea (0.50 % UW and 0.31 % MTW) and fungi (0.33 % UW and 0.21 % MTW) (Fig. 2). To evaluate the effect of the microalgae treatment on the microbial communities, changes at the phylum and the most abundant species were evaluated. At the phylum level, the most abundant and with the biggest differences were found for the Pseudomonadota, increasing their abundance a 15 % after algae treatment (67.31 % MTW vs. 52.04 % UW) and Actinomycetota, decreasing their abundance after water purification (23.64 % MTW vs. 34.34 % UW). At the species level there were important changes in the abundance of the top 10 most abundant bacterial taxa (Table 3). Notably, *Porphyrobacter* sp. HT-58-2

Table 3

Top 10 most abundant species per domain found in the drain water samples from soilless tomato crop.

UW	%	%	MTW
Bacteria			
<i>Mycobacterium conspicuum</i>	3.31	6.22	<i>Porphyrobacter</i> sp. HT-58-2
<i>Mycobacterium colombiense</i>	2.21	4.78	<i>Porphyrobacter</i> sp. YT40
<i>Acinetobacter johnsonii</i>	1.93	3.28	<i>Erythrobacter</i> sp. BLCC-B19
<i>Micromonospora</i> sp. WMMA2032	1.53	2.99	<i>Porphyrobacter</i> sp. CACIAM 03H1
<i>Klebsiella aerogenes</i>	1.51	2.87	<i>Erythrobacter</i> sp.
<i>Bosea beijingensis</i>	1.16	2.76	<i>Porphyrobacter</i> sp. LM 6
<i>Mycobacterium intracellulare</i>	1.05	2.35	Uncultured <i>Erythrobacter</i> sp.
<i>Bosea</i> sp. ANAM02	1.01	2.25	<i>Porphyrobacter</i> sp. ULC335
<i>Oscillatoria nigro-viridis</i>	0.95	1.82	<i>Erythrobacter neustonensis</i>
<i>Porphyrobacter</i> sp. HT-58-2	0.90	1.35	<i>Roseicyclus marinus</i>
Archaea			
<i>Candidatus Nitrosotalea okcheonensis</i>	5.72	1.63	<i>Halomicrococcus gelatinilyticus</i>
<i>Nitrososphaera viennensis</i>	2.30	1.43	<i>Halomarina</i> sp. BND7
<i>Candidatus Nitrososphaera evergladensis</i>	1.57	1.43	<i>Halosimplex aquaticum</i>
<i>Halosimplex aquaticum</i>	1.45	1.37	<i>Halorussus vallis</i>
<i>Halorussus vallis</i>	1.35	1.33	<i>Halomicrobium salinisoli</i>
<i>Halomicrobium salinisoli</i>	1.21	1.24	<i>Halobaculum</i> sp. XH14
<i>Halomicrococcus gelatinilyticus</i>	0.87	1.21	<i>Halomarina</i> sp. PSR21
<i>Haloglomis halophilum</i>	0.86	1.19	<i>Salinirubellus</i> sp. SYNS196
<i>Halorussus limi</i>	0.85	1.15	<i>Haloferax gibbonsii</i>
<i>Halapricum desulfuricans</i>	0.81	1.14	<i>Halobaculum roseum</i>
Fungi			
<i>Trichoderma breve</i>	7.11	4.80	<i>Vanrija pseudolonga</i>
<i>Vanrija pseudolonga</i>	3.33	4.33	<i>Malassezia japonica</i>
<i>Purpureocillium takamizusanense</i>	3.28	4.27	<i>Thermothielavioides terrestris</i>
<i>Thermothielavioides terrestris</i>	3.05	4.23	<i>Pyricularia pennisetigena</i>
<i>Pyricularia pennisetigena</i>	2.95	3.74	<i>Purpureocillium takamizusanense</i>
<i>Ascochyta rabiei</i>	2.90	2.82	<i>Akanthomyces muscarius</i>
<i>Colletotrichum higginsianum</i>	2.72	2.73	<i>Ustilagoidea virens</i>
<i>Drechmeria coniospora</i>	2.68	2.63	<i>Colletotrichum higginsianum</i>
<i>Malassezia japonica</i>	2.52	2.60	<i>Thermothelomyces thermophilus</i>

UW: untreated water. MTW: microalgae treated water (MTW)

was the only bacterial species found to be highly abundant in both the untreated and treated water samples.

Comparing the potential agricultural benefits and drawbacks associated with each bacterial community reveals significant differences. The UW community presented several potential advantages, including the presence of *Acinetobacter johnsonii* and *Klebsiella aerogenes*, both known for their plant growth-promoting capabilities (Shi et al., 2011; Ou et al., 2022). Additionally, the UW community included *Bosea* spp,

Fig. 2. Relative abundances of phyla more abundant in water samples. UW: Untreated water, MTW: Microalgae treated water.

and some members of this genus is known by their bioremediation potential (Lu et al., 2018; Yan et al., 2022). However, the UW community also included *Mycobacterium conspicuum* and *Mycobacterium colombiense*, which are classified as potential opportunistic pathogens (Pavlik, 2022), representing a potential drawback for the agricultural use of this untreated water.

The MTW community, resulting from the microalgae treatment, showed a different profile. The abundance of *Erythrobacter* species, with potential to produce carotenoids (Takaichi et al., 1990), known antioxidants, give them an advantage to survive in the oxidant conditions created by microalgae through the O₂ release due to their photosynthetic activity. A potential benefit of the MTW community is the absence of the potential opportunistic pathogens identified in the UW sample. However, the MTW community also lacks the prominent plant growth promoters found in the UW, which could be a disadvantage from an agricultural perspective.

The archaeal communities also exhibited a diverse range of potential agricultural functions. The UW sample harbors a significant community of ammonia-oxidizing archaea (*Candidatus Nitrosotalea okcheonensis*, *Nitrososphaera viennensis*, and *Candidatus Nitrososphaera evergladensis*) (Stieglmeier et al., 2014; Zhalnina et al., 2014; Herbold et al., 2017) that likely play a crucial role in nitrification, converting ammonia from plant waste and nutrient solutions into plant-available nitrate. However, *Halorussus vallis* can reduce nitrate to nitrite, without gas formation (Zheng et al., 2022), which could influence the nitrogen balance in the UW sample, potentially impacting the availability of nitrate for plant uptake. Besides, *Halapricum desulfuricans* could be involved in sulfur cycling due to the capacity of anaerobic respiration using sulfur compounds (Sorokin et al., 2021). Despite, several archaea species maintain their abundance relatively stable with the microalgae treatment (*Halomicrococcus gelatinilyticus*, *Halosimplex aquaticum*, *Halorussus vallis*, *Halomicrobium salinisoli*), the previous mentioned taxa involved in the N and P cycles diminished their abundance considerably. Besides, it promoted the growth of other halophilic archaea, which suggested a better adaptation to the microalgae environment.

The most abundant fungus in the UW was *Trichoderma breve*. The genus *Trichoderma* is a well-known in agriculture, primarily as a biofungicide for the control of a broad spectrum of plant diseases (Tyśkiewicz et al., 2022). For instance, *Trichoderma breve* Z2-03 demonstrated a significant 74.17 % inhibition against *Rhizoctonia solani*, a pathogen causing sheath blight in rice (Intana et al., 2024). This antagonistic activity is partly attributed to the release of lytic enzymes by *Trichoderma* (Natsiopoulou et al., 2024). Besides, *Trichoderma breve* isolate Z2-03 has been shown to produce indole-3-acetic acid, which can promote plant growth and development (Intana et al., 2024). *Purpureocillium takamizusanense* is an entomopathogenic fungus that has shown significant promise for biological pest control in agriculture (Pei-Hsin, 2025). Isolate TCTeb01 of this species has exhibited high pathogenicity against a variety of agricultural pests, including the lychee stink bug, melon thrips, and coffee berry borer. Notably, this fungus also possesses a remarkable capacity for phosphate solubilization, reaching levels of 4672.1 µg mL⁻¹ day⁻¹, indicating its potential as a valuable biofertilizer. Field tests with TCTeb01 have shown plant growth promotion in various vegetable crops, including a 20 % increase in plant weight in cabbage and a 15 % increase in yield for water spinach (Pei-Hsin, 2025). *Thermothielavioides terrestris*, is a thermophilic fungus renowned for its production of a variety of thermostable enzymes, including cellulases and hemicellulases (Alnoch et al., 2023). *Thermothielavioides terrestris* plays a role in the global carbon cycle by facilitating the decomposition of biomass polysaccharides (Berka et al., 2011). *Drechmeria coniospora* is considered a potential biocontrol agent for managing nematode populations in agricultural settings (Lebrigand et al., 2016). However, some species can result pathogenic in plant. *Pyricularia pennisetigena*, present in both water samples, is a pathogen that causes leaf blast disease in various grasses, including king grass, and has shown the ability to infect important crops like rice and wheat (Liu et al., 2024). *Ascochyta rabiei*, is

a devastating pathogen of chickpea, causing Ascochyta blight (Foresto et al., 2023).

The presence of seven of the top ten most abundant fungal species in both the MTW and UW samples suggests that the algae treatment had no substantial impact on the composition of this group of microorganisms. However, the most abundant taxa in UW (*Trichoderma breve*), with prominent plant growth promoting features, reduced its abundance from 7.11 % to 1.88 %, coming off from the Top 10 ranking. However, this microorganism can be recovered since the inputs of the intensive agriculture in the Almerian region usually include microorganisms from this genus due to their well known properties.

Anyway, some of the Top 10 fungi species found in the MTW sample are of particular interest. Like that, *Akanthomyces muscarius*, which is an entomopathogenic fungus that has been commercialized as a biological control agent for managing insect pests, particularly whiteflies and aphids, in greenhouses (Erdos et al., 2023). Besides, *Akanthomyces muscarius* may possess biocontrol potential against certain plant pathogenic fungi, such as *Fusarium* and *Curvularia* (Saidi et al., 2023). On the contrary, *Ustilagoidea vires* is a fungal pathogen that causes false smut disease in rice, leading to significant reductions in grain yield and quality (Sunani et al., 2024). *Thermothelomyces thermophilus*, is known by the production of thermostable lignocellulolytic enzymes, which secretes to degrade biomass lignocellulosic materials (Siebecker et al., 2023). Notably, *Thermothelomyces thermophilus* produces phytase, an enzyme that can improve nutrient availability by releasing bound phosphorus, which is crucial for plant growth (Rohr et al., 2025).

As a remark, the microalgae treatment clearly had an important impact in the microbial communities of the water samples, especially in the bacteria species. The elimination of potential pathogens is a positive outcome that could enhance the safety of reusing the treated water for irrigation.

3.2.2. Functional annotations

Based on the Kegg orthology database functional genes related to C, N and P cycles were pooled together and classified on different processes (Fig. 3) according to Du et al. (2023). Related to C cycle, organic matter degradation and C fixation (photosynthetic activity) genes abundances were evaluated (Fig. 3a and b). In both water samples, genes related to the degradation of the more recalcitrant form of organic matter (lignin) accounted for the higher abundance. This result was a bit surprising because crops used in the soilless crop do not contain high fractions of this C fraction. It was also notably that MTW sample contained more relative abundance genes related to the degradation of this polymer and to the more labile (starch) form of organic matter (Fig. 3b). On the contrary, UW sample contained more gene abundance related to the degradation of the labile form of hemicellulose. Another unexpected result was the relatively more abundance of C fixation genes in the UT sample. This shows that microalgae purification is useful in organic matter degradation of plant debris (Mohsenpour et al., 2021) and that microalgae removal in the purified water is extremely efficient.

Associated to the N cycle, the most abundant processes identified were degradation of N compounds present in organic matter (more abundant in UW) and the denitrification processes (especially more abundant in MTW) (Fig. 3c). On this case, the use of purified water was less interesting in terms of soil fertility. On the one hand, the N mineralization processes were less promoted, and on the other hand, the use of MTW could result in the loss of N plant bioavailable form (nitrate) through the formation of N₂O or N₂ gases resulting of denitrification processes (Shakeel et al., 2024).

Linked to P cycle, genes relative abundance was higher in MTW sample for all the processes studied (Fig. 3d). In terms of soil fertility, inorganic P solubilization and organic P mineralization increase the bioavailable forms of P in soil. In basic soils, majority in the southeastern of Iberian Peninsula, the P coming from soluble fertilizers precipitates in an important fraction in form of calcium phosphates. Some microorganisms have the ability to solubilize the inorganic P (E.g. through the

Fig. 3. Gene RPK Relative abundances grouped by biogeochemical cycles and processes. ANRA: Assimilatory nitrate reduction to ammonium. DNRA: dissimilatory nitrate reduction to ammonium. UW: untreated water. MTW: microalgae treated water.

excretion of acids), which can enhance the crop productivity (Ortega et al., 2023). Besides, P mineralization processes are the main source of nutrients for plants through the degradation of organic matter (Raguet et al., 2023). The use of the purified water with agronomic purposes, both in conventional agriculture based on synthetic fertilizers and in organic agriculture based on organic fertilizers. Finally, P uptake and transport processes result in the immobilization of P due to the incorporation in the structure of microorganisms. However, a C:P ratio between 200 and 300 in soils can support a balanced microbial activity and nutrient mineralization (Pagani et al., 2013).

3.3. Evaluation of fertigation treatments on lettuce crop

Water obtained from microalgae-based phytoremediation contains residual microalgae, which can have a biostimulant effect when used for irrigation. The lettuce cultivar 'Maravilla de Verano' has been used in research because it is sensitive to the salinity of irrigation water, making it a reliable indicator of the potential biostimulant effects of irrigation treatments (Cunha-Chiamolera et al., 2024).

3.3.1. Effects on monitoring parameters of fertigation

The fertigation and drainage ratio, EC, and pH of drains are the frequent fertigation parameters that are utilized for control and feedback of each new nutrient solution supplied (Savvas, 2002; Schröder and Lieth, 2002; Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009). The drainage percentage values for all fertigation system treatments that were tested remained constant at 15–20 % (data not shown). These results of the ratio between fertigation and its drainage value indicates that the optimal matric potential has been maintained (Peçanha et al., 2021). There were no significant differences in the EC and pH of the drain water from any of the fertigation treatments evaluated (Fig. 4). The mean values of EC (b) and pH (d) of the effluents were approximately 1 dS m⁻¹ and 0.5 units higher than their supply values, respectively, indicating no potential osmotic stress or, alternatively, significant changes in nutrient uptake.

Fertigation drainage monitoring parameters (EC and pH) showed no correlation with fertigation uptake parameters (water, nitrate, and potassium) or growth parameters (root, stem, and leaves) (Table 4), suggesting that the fertigation process was well-controlled."

3.3.2. Effect fertigation uptake parameters and environmental emissions

To assess the effectiveness and efficiency of fertigation on production process and to minimize the emission of potential environmental pollutants, key fertigation uptake parameters - water, nitrate and potassium - are generally monitored. Fertigation uptake was strongly correlated with final yield, particularly in terms of fresh weight (Table 4). There was no correlation between fertigation uptake and the roots. A significant correlation was recorded between water, nitrate and potassium uptake and fresh weight, but not with dry weight. Among the fertigation uptake parameters examined in this study (water, nitrate, and potassium), water uptake showed the strongest correlation with fresh weight. The percentage of water absorbed was the most reliable indicator of final yield, a finding previously observed by Cunha-Chiamolera et al. (2023) and Rincón-Cervera et al. (2024) under similar crop conditions. Throughout crop, the treatments using MTW (TAs and TAg) had a higher uptake than the others (Fig. 5a). The improvement in water absorbed with the algae treatment increased significantly, by 5.7 % for good and sub-optimal water quality, respectively. Nitrate absorbed proved to be comparable to that of water (Fig. 5b). Nonetheless, the results indicated that in the specific case under consideration, the utilization of water of suboptimum quality (T0m vs. T0g) led to a substantial decline in its absorption (11 %) due to osmotic pressure; meanwhile, the use of water from tomato crop drains treated with microalgae (T0m vs. TAg) compensated for the reduction in absorption caused by osmotic pressure (T0m vs. T0g). Significant differences were also observed in potassium absorption. These results may be similar to those found by Sarsekeyeva et al. (2024), who highlighted that microalgae and cyanobacteria extracts promote plant tolerance to salt and osmotic stress by activating antioxidant mechanisms, thereby

Fig. 4. Electrical conductivity (EC) (a) and pH (c) of the lettuce plant drains during crop cycle and their mean values (b and d, respectively) comparing the use of water irrigation from the tomato crop drain with microalgae depuration versus a control. Different letters indicate significant differences by Tukey test at $p \leq 0.05$.

Table 4

Pearson correlation matrix for results of parameter controlled of fertigation and growth for microalgae-treated drainage water supplied by fertigation in lettuce grown under soilless culture.

		Drainage		Uptake			Fresh Weight				Dry Weight		
		EC	pH	Water	NO ₃ ⁻	K ⁺	Leaves	Stem	Root	Total	Leaves	Stem	Root
Drainage	pH	0.128 ^{ns}	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Uptake	Water	-0.277 ^{ns}	-0.506 ^{ns}	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	NO ₃ ⁻	-0.071 ^{ns}	-0.460 ^{ns}	0.885 ^{****}	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	K ⁺	0.038 ^{ns}	-0.259 ^{ns}	0.487 ^{ns}	0.533 [*]	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fresh	Leaves	-0.067 ^{ns}	-0.508 ^{ns}	0.680 ^{**}	0.647 ^{**}	0.751 ^{**}	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Weight	Stem	-0.101 ^{ns}	-0.400 ^{ns}	0.612 [*]	0.562 [*]	0.147 ^{ns}	0.393 ^{ns}	—	—	—	—	—	—
	Root	0.030 ^{ns}	-0.185 ^{ns}	0.037 ^{ns}	0.124 ^{ns}	0.140 ^{ns}	0.295 ^{ns}	0.207 ^{ns}	—	—	—	—	—
	Total	-0.059 ^{ns}	-0.515 ^{ns}	0.655 ^{**}	0.638 ^{**}	0.718 ^{**}	0.983 ^{****}	0.439 ^{ns}	0.457 ^{ns}	—	—	—	—
Dry	Leaves	-0.239 ^{ns}	-0.207 ^{ns}	0.491 ^{ns}	0.428 ^{ns}	0.270 ^{ns}	0.655 ^{**}	0.359 ^{ns}	0.490 ^{ns}	0.702 ^{**}	—	—	—
	Stem	-0.008 ^{ns}	-0.196 ^{ns}	0.243 ^{ns}	0.259 ^{ns}	-0.248 ^{ns}	0.115 ^{ns}	0.816 ^{***}	0.455 ^{ns}	0.222 ^{ns}	0.374 ^{ns}	—	—
	Root	0.237 ^{ns}	-0.153 ^{ns}	-0.145 ^{ns}	0.063 ^{ns}	0.057 ^{ns}	0.162 ^{ns}	0.137 ^{ns}	0.759 ^{***}	0.289 ^{ns}	0.441 ^{ns}	0.400 ^{ns}	—
	Total	-0.141 ^{ns}	-0.226 ^{ns}	0.390 ^{ns}	0.394 ^{ns}	0.214 ^{ns}	0.591 [*]	0.406 ^{ns}	0.629 [*]	0.670 ^{**}	0.967 ^{****}	0.499 ^{ns}	0.641 ^{**}

****, ***, **, *, and ns indicant significant at $P \leq 0.001$, $P \leq 0.01$, $P \leq 0.05$, $P \leq 0.10$ or not significant, respectively. n = 8.

contributing to improved osmotic adjustment and ionic homeostasis under adverse conditions.

The results on uptake fertigation parameters generally indicated that osmotic pressure had a negative effect (T0m vs T0g), whereas the use of microalgae-treated drainage had a positive effect (TAg vs T0g, and TAM vs T0m). This suggests that the presence of the microalgae culture enhanced fertigation uptake (water, nitrate and potassium), likely due to its biostimulant properties (Nordio et al., 2024). Microalgae can improve nutrient assimilation in plants by producing bioactive compounds, enhancing root activity, or modifying microbial communities,

similar results were also reported by Cunha-Chiamolera et al. (2024). The result showed that when drain from tomato crops was used without the microalgae-crop, either with good (TSg) or sub-optimal water quality (TSm), nitrate uptake was like their controls (T0g and T0m, respectively). This result showed that within the specified range of fertigation EC for lettuce crops, there was no significant impact on nitrate uptake conditions. This suggests that factors other than fertigation EC or pH levels, such as biological activity, nutrient availability, or plant physiology of the roots, may have a more substantial influence on nitrate uptake.

Fig. 5. Water (a), nitrate (c) and potassium (e) uptake of the lettuce plant during crop cycle and their total values (b, d and f, respectively) comparing the use of water irrigation from the tomato crop drain with microalgae depuration versus a control. Different letters indicate significant differences by Tukey test at $p \leq 0.05$.

In the experimental setting, the drains treated with the microalgae culture showed increased nitrate uptake when operated under conditions of good or sub-optimal water quality, in comparison to the other treatments (Fig. 5c and d). The TAg treatment resulted in a 5.7 % increase in nitrate uptake in comparison to T0g and TSg, and TAs showed a 5.1 % increase in comparison to T0m and TSm, respectively. This enhanced nitrate uptake leads to a significant reduction in nitrate emissions, thereby minimizing soil contamination and mitigating eutrophication in groundwater, as well as in adjacent rivers and lakes. It

was observed that the trend in potassium uptake exhibited a striking similarity to the nitrate uptake trend in all fertigation systems. The results showed a highly statistically significant reduction in potassium uptake when optimal water was used as opposed to sub-optimal water (more than 80 % reduction); while the same comparison for nitrate uptake registered a value of 15 %. Potassium uptake was significantly enhanced in the microalgae treatment under suboptimal conditions compared to treatments that did not utilize drainage from the microalgae crop (Fig. 5e and f). The presence of microbial genes related to P

uptake was also promoted in this treatment (Fig. 3d). Although the presence of potassium in drainage discharged into the environment is not considered as pollution, the enhanced uptake of this nutrient ion is a clear indicator of an important benefit to the plant indicating that microalgae treatment of drainage results in a significant biostimulant effect.

3.3.3. Effect on yield and growth parameters

All growth parameters and yield varied significantly by the evaluated fertigation systems (Fig. 6). These results suggest that, under optimal microclimatic conditions for crop growth and cultural management and when maintaining other fertigation parameters, such as substrate matric potential, the composition of the nutrient solution is a decisive factor in influencing plant growth, nutrient uptake and overall yield. Both the fresh and dry weights were affected by different fertigation treatments. The leaves were the organs in which the effect of the different treatments was most significant, while in the stems, and especially in the roots, there was no clear effect of the treatments evaluated.

3.3.3.1. Salinity effect ("X" g vs. "X" m). It has been well known since the work of Maas and Hoffman (1977) and up to the present day (Rincón-Cervera et al., 2024) that salinity is one of the main abiotic stresses, commonly monitored through the electrical conductivity (EC) of irrigation water. On the other hand, lettuce is considered a salt-sensitive crop (Maas and Hoffman, 1977) and is widely regarded as a model species due to its representative physiological response, making it a paradigm in horticultural irrigation research.

The results varied when comparing the effect salinity (good vs. medium-quality irrigation water, 'X' g vs. 'X' m). For roots and stem no significant differences were found between salinity treatments. Conversely, when no drainage water from the tomato crop was reused

(T0g vs. T0m), a significant decrease in leaf fresh weight and overall plant growth was observed, attributed to the salinity of the fertigation.

The number and proportion of significant differences in fresh weight were greater than dry weight, so that the effect of the different treatments more clearly affected fresh weight than dry weight. The use of poor-quality water with a higher initial salinity (T0g vs. T0m) caused a significant reduction of 28 % and 27 % in the fresh weight of the plants in leaves and total, respectively. These results suggest that while the treatments had a significant effect on fresh weight, they did not have a statistically significant effect on dry weight. This implies that the primary impact of the treatments was on the water content of the crop rather than on its accumulated biomass. Similar results for the crop of lettuce under soilless culture have already been reported by Cunha-Chiamolera et al. (2024), and for other plants considered to be halophytes such as ice plant Rincón-Cervera et al. (2024).

3.3.3.2. Effect of reusing tomato crop drains. In any case (T0g vs. TSg and T0m vs. TSm), reusing drainage from tomato cultivation had no phytotoxic or adverse effect on growth or production. Even in the case of using poor quality water for leaf fresh weight and total fresh weight, a significant benefit was found (6.06 %). That is, based on our data across 16 growth parameters, we can confirm that the use of drainage from a tomato crop in soilless culture systems could be safely reused, as it does not produce any negative or phytotoxic effects on lettuce crop. The presence of plant growth-promoting microorganisms in tomato crop drains could be related to their beneficial effect found.

For decades, it has been well known that recirculating drainage in soilless cultivation systems is an effective way of saving water and fertiliser (Schröder and Lieth, 2002; Asaduzzaman et al., 2022; Urrestarazu and Carrasco, 2023). Nonetheless, our results suggest the presence of a novel factor that may enhance the biostimulation process by promoting

T0g = optimum irrigation water (g) + fertilizer (CF); **TSg** = g + untreated drain water (S) + CF; **TAg** = g + microalgae-treated drain water (A) + fertilizer (CF); **T0m** = suboptimum irrigation water (m) + CF; **TSm** = m + S + CF; **TAm** = m + A + CF.

Fig. 6. Fresh (a and b) and dry (c and d) weight of lettuce plant under different fertigation systems comparing the use of water irrigation from the tomato crop drain with microalgae depuration versus a control. Different letters indicate significant differences between lettuce parts or total lettuce parts by Tukey test at $p \leq 0.05$.

the growth of beneficial microbiota.

3.3.3.3. Effect of reusing tomato crop drains through microalgae-based purification. When comparing the results of the drainage of the tomato crop treated and not treated with microalgae in both good (TA_g vs. TS_g) and sub-optimal (TA_m vs. TO_m) water quality conditions, only significant differences are in favour of the treated crop (For stem fresh weight and total dry weight).

The use of water from microalgae purification did not result in any negative effects when compared to controls of both good (TA_g vs. TO_g) and sub-optimal (TA_m vs. TO_m) water quality. Of the eight growth parameters (root, stem, leaf and total -fresh and dry weight) and production evaluated, 8 of 16 significant positive values are reached (TA_g vs. TO_g or TA_m vs. TO_m) by using water treated with microalgae. This improvement represented a percentage increase of 21.7 %.

The difference in microbiota reported in the microalgae-treated waters (TA_g vs. TS_g and TA_m vs. TS_m) could be related to their potential biostimulant effect, given that using these waters increases biomass production overall compared to using other waters. Similar growing conditions and using lettuce as the model crop, related findings were reported by Ergun et al. (2020) with the microalga *Chlorella vulgaris* as a biostimulant, by Cunha-Chiamolera et al. (2024) with consortia of microalgae and bacteria exist, and by Julia et al. (2020) and Chaski and Petropoulos (2022) using various seaweed extracts.

3.4. Alleviative effects of water from microalgae-based purification on salinity stress (TO_g vs. TA_m)

Salt stress is well known to be a major environmental factor limiting plant growth and crop productivity (Hashemi et al., 2010), and recently some progress has been made in understanding the potential mechanisms by which certain forms of active matter alleviate salt stress (Zhu et al., 2014). On the other hand, it has been described how various substances can act as biostimulants through fertigation to alleviate the decrease in yield of salt stress sensitive plants (Chaski and Petropoulos, 2022; Ferrón-Carrillo et al., 2022).

The addition of microalgae-purified water to tomato crop drainage with poor-quality water (TA_m) effectively compensated for the production loss typically associated with salt stress, yielding results comparable to those obtained under optimal fertigation with good-quality water (TO_g).

Algae purification treatments were effective in alleviating salinity stress, as evidenced by improved physiological and yield parameters under sub-optimal fertigation regimes.

4. Conclusions

This study shows that microalgae-based treatment of horticultural drainage water offers an effective approach to wastewater recycling, enhancing horticultural yield, and generating valuable algal biomass for use as fertilizer.

The process significantly reduces the concentration of key ions, thereby improving the quality of reclaimed water for irrigation without compromising microalgal biomass productivity, which was shown to match levels typically achieved using synthetic culture media. This confirms the suitability of agricultural drainage as a cost-effective and sustainable medium for *Scenedesmus* sp. cultivation.

Importantly, while the use of microalgae reduces some plant growth-promoting microorganisms, it concurrently leads to a marked reduction in potential phytopathogens, enhancing the microbial safety of irrigation water. Furthermore, functional microbial genes involved in biogeochemical cycling—particularly those linked to carbon degradation, phosphorus solubilization, and mineralization—were enriched in the treated water. This suggests that microalgae-treated effluents may enhance soil fertility and crop performance, especially in systems using

organic amendments or alkaline soils where phosphorus bioavailability is typically limited due to precipitation.

Beyond purification, the treated water exhibited biostimulant properties, contributing to improved nutrient uptake, higher fertigation efficiency, and enhanced crop yields. It also helped mitigate the osmotic stress often caused by saline drainage reuse. Thus, this approach not only provides environmental and agronomic benefits but also represents a scalable, circular economy model that supports resource recovery, reduces pollutant discharge, and enhances farm profitability. The integration of microalgae treatment into horticultural practices stands out as a sustainable innovation for water reuse and soil-health management in intensive agriculture.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

P.L. Cunha-Chiamolera Tatiana: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Miguel Urrestarazu:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Francisco Gabriel Acién Fernández:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Cintia Gómez-Serrano:** Writing – review & editing. **Adrián Guirao-García:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Silvia Jimenez-Becker:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Raúl Ortega:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Isabel Miralles:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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